

Overtourism in India: Impacts, Challenges, and Solutions for Sustainable Destinations

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Abstract: Overtourism occurs when the number of tourists within a destination surpasses its carrying capacity. It has justly become an extremely pressing global concern, notably affecting places such as Venice, Barcelona, and the Maldives. This tourist inflow, in the face of low-cost travel, its subsequent demand driven by social media, and greatly improved worldwide mobility, has become strong drivers of essential negative impacts on the environment, local communities, and cultural heritage. Such are environmental, pertaining to pollution and habitat destruction, social, related to the displacing of residents and cultural dilution, and economic, in that tourism revenues are very unevenly distributed. In fact, this will call for multilevel control of overtourism, which shall involve enhancing sustainable tourism practices, improving infrastructure, and stakeholder involvement in strategic planning. Solutions have to aim at preserving natural and cultural integrity at destinations while keeping economic viability. Effective management strategies balance tourism benefits against destination protection through diversification, visitor management, and community involvement.

Keywords: Overtourism, Sustainable Tourism, Environmental Degradation, Cultural Heritage, Strategic Planning.

1. INTRODUCTION TO OVERTOURISM

Overtourism is described as a phenomenon that, of late, has emerged as one of the major challenges facing popular tourist destinations around the world, characterized by excessive visitor inflows that negatively affect the environment, local communities, and cultural heritage (UNWTO, 2018). The UNWTO defines it as "the impact of tourism on a destination, or parts thereof, which excessively influences perceived quality of life of residents or visitors in a negative way, and more specifically, causes unfavourable economic, social, and environmental effects." Because destinations such as Venice, Barcelona, and the Maldives have been experiencing the worst effects of mass tourism, this concept has received wide attention in recent years. Overtourism is a term that describes the sum of the problems that arise when a place cannot handle any longer the number of tourists, and it starts polluting the environment, disrupting the locals' daily life, and even challenging the cultural authenticity of the destination (Milano, Cheer, & Novelli, 2019).

Fast development of international tourism due to low travel costs, the power of social media, and higher mobility in the world has additionally increased the problem of overtourism (Goodwin, 2017). Although tourism is an integrated economic driver, providing both money and jobs to local economies, it has major disadvantages when expanding unregulated. Environmental disadvantages range from pollution to wildcat deforestation and depletion of resources; the social ones include everything from displacement of residents and rising living costs to erosion of cultural identity and many others (Dodds & Butler, 2019). Socially, the influx of tourists can disrupt local communities, leading to tensions between visitors and residents, and contributing to the loss of cultural heritage as traditional practices are replaced by tourism-driven activities (Butler R., 2018). The economic impact will involve the generation of large revenues; however, some are not usually adequately shared in the host communities and in most cases foster inequality amongst them (Gössling S., Tourism, tourists, and sustainability., 2019).

It also poses a risk to the sustainability of tourism destinations, primarily in terms of holding up visitor satisfaction while protecting and conserving both natural and cultural resources (Seraphin, Sheeran, & Pilato, 2018). An overtourism solution must be relatively holistic, including good sustainable tourism practice, policy response, and stakeholder

reaction. Most importantly, for the betterment of the visited places and for the long-term sustainability of the tourism flow, strategies need to be developed to handle visitor pressures, especially regarding destination promotion and adequate investment in infrastructure for sustainable development (UNWTO, 2018).

2. HISTORICAL CONTEXT AND EMERGENCE

"Overtourism" is a fairly new term, but it has been major in the early 21st century, when tourism numbers took off worldwide. Historically, tourism has been viewed as an economic windfall, generating employment and spurring the local economy. With a quickly rising number of international travellers due to affordable fares, the rise of budget airlines, and online travel platforms, many destinations are experiencing a marked rise in visitor numbers (Butler R. W., 1980). But the actual turnaround came in the 1990s and early 2000s when travel was actually beginning to democratize with the infiltration of digital technologies. A platform like Airbnb and social media sites like Instagram have been key drivers of visitors to previously relatively unknown destinations, which have suddenly experienced an unexpected boom in tourism (Gössling, Scott, & Hall, 2019). Cities such as Venice, Barcelona, and Dubrovnik became symbols of overtourism, representing congested streets, the overburdening of public services, and diluted local cultures (Koens, Postma, & Papp, 2018).

As overtourism's consequences are becoming more recognized, overtourism has turned into a worldwide concern which advocates for more sustainable and responsible tourism. Scholars and policymakers have then begun to call to action the implementation of visitor management practices, encouragement of the availability of alternative destinations, and policy formulation regarding the trade-offs of the industry between tourism benefits and the preservation of the environment and the community (Peeters, Gössling, Klijs, & Milano, 2018).

3. CAUSES OF OVERTOURISM

1. **Increased Global Mobility:** The major underlying cause of overtourism is the increased rate of global mobility. Enhancements in transportation, especially with the rise of low-cost airways, have made the idea of literally crossing borders a lot more within reach for the common man or woman (Gössling & Peeters, 2007). When you can conveniently book a flight online and the facilities and connectivity of a place are improving, the unbridled movement of people across borders becomes feasible. According to the UNWTO, international tourist arrivals, in 2018, hit 1.4 billion, markedly better than the past decades, evidencing the boom in global travel (UNWTO., 2019).
2. **Rise of Social Media and Digital Influence:** Social media and digital platforms have equally been significant drivers of overtourism. Places have been popularized through such popular media on the internet like Instagram, Facebook, travel blogs, and so on, which often emphasize highly aesthetic locations, which before were quite unknown. (Gössling S. , Tourism, tourist learning and sustainability: An exploratory discussion of complexities, problems and opportunities, 2018). The "Instagrammability" of destinations has become a key factor in travel decisions, leading to sudden and intense spikes in visitor numbers (Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014). The bandwagon effect is created by influencers and user-generated content when travellers flock to destinations that gain popularity without considering the sustainability or capacity of those places to be able to handle large crowds.
3. **Economic Factors and Affordability of Travel:** Increasing disposable incomes in emerging markets, along with the overall affordability of global travel, in general, have been significant factors that contribute to overtourism. The rise in the middle class in areas such as China and India has indeed increased the size of the global travel market, when growth of the middle class directly correlates with higher tourist volumes (UNWTO., 2019). For this reason, with competitive pricing from airlines, hotels, and travel agencies, traveling truly is more affordable than it has been in the past (Gössling & Peeters, 2007). Budgetary accommodations and sharing economy websites like Airbnb have decreased the costs, thereby allowing more individuals to travel more often and to new destinations as a result (Guttentag, 2015).

4. IMPACTS OF OVERTOURISM

1. **Environmental Degradation:** Natural Habitats Destruction: The most visible impact of overtourism is the environmental degradation of natural habitats. This is due to the fact that the tourist attractions often face extreme ecological strain as a result of the large number of visitor arrivals. Final: Fragile ecosystems such as coral reefs, forests, and coastal areas suffer from effects such as trampling, littering, and tourism void of any policies (Barker & Roberts, 2008). Severe coral bleaching has, for instance, been experienced in the Great Barrier Reef, caused in part by the growth in tourist activities and climate change (Hughes, 2017).

2. **Pollution and Waste Management** Because of the altered tourist numbers, there is generation of more wastes than usual, and very few destinations have mechanisms in place to withstand it. Unrestricted waste disposal practices and inadequate treatment and disposal of sewage may bring about contamination of water and land, thereby adversely impacting the environment and human health likewise (Cole & Razak, 2009). Another factor is the high air pollution resulting from more emissions from automobiles and other tourism-related operations, which increases the pace of environmental deterioration patterns together with climate change (Gössling & Peeters, 2007).
3. **Social and Cultural Impacts: Displacement of Residents** The high number of tourist visits may displace the local residents of the hosting area, more so in cities and popular destinations. Growing demand for rental houses and accommodation increases the prices and rent, making it difficult and unaffordable for locals to continue living in their communities (Guttentag, 2015). This displacement can lead to a loss of community and the erosion of local identities and traditions (Martín M, 2018).
4. **Cultural Dilution and Loss of Heritage** The commodification of local cultures usually fits the tourist, thus almost always resulting in an erosion of authentic cultural practices and traditions. In most cases, tourist-driven development may result to focusing on commercial interests at the expense of preserving the cultural heritage sites, which then deteriorate or are lost (Russo & van der Borg, 2002). This can, for instance, point out to how difficult it has been for cities like Venice to maintain its cultural heritage against the overwhelming number of visiting tourists (Seraphin H. S., 2018).
5. **Economic Effects: Uneven Distribution of Tourism Revenue:** Economically, overtourism may bring about an uneven distribution of the revenue accrued through tourism. Whereas tourism could yield tremendous economic gain, such gains always accrue to a few businesses or investors compared to the local economy itself (Sinclair, 1998). This can exacerbate economic inequalities and limit the broader community's ability to benefit from tourism.
6. **Rising Property Prices:** Tourist accommodation can cause property prices to rise, making housing affordable for local residents. This has been witnessed in many countries, where favorite tourists' destinations have witnessed a dramatic increase in property values and rental costs as a result of the proliferation of platforms such as Airbnb (Crommelin, Troy, Martin, & Pettit, 2018). This can result in housing shortages and gentrification, displacing people who have resided in these areas for long and altering the social character of communities (Wachsmuth & Weisler, 2018).

5. INDIA'S POSITION ON OVERTOURISM

India, a country known for its rich cultural heritage and diverse landscapes, has been experiencing significant growth in tourism. This influx of tourists, while beneficial economically, has brought about the challenges of overtourism. Overtourism is "excessive tourism to the point where destinations suffer" and this is becoming a major concern for many popular tourist spots in India. Tourism is one of the significant aspects that drive the increments in GDP and employment in India's economy. World Travel and Tourism Council stated that revenues of \$194 billion caused tourism to contribute to 6.8 percent of India's GDP and more than 40 million jobs in 2019 (WTTC, 2020). However, the downside of this boom is the pressure it puts on infrastructure and local communities. Popular destinations like Goa, Kerala, Rajasthan, and the Himalayan states suffer from an acute strain of overtourism. Goa is popular for its beaches, yet excessive littering and undeterred construction play a role in environmental degradation and water pollution (Raut & Jadhav, 2018). Kerala's backwaters and houseboat tourism have led to water pollution and loss of aquatic life (Ghosh, 2019). In such a culturally rich state like Rajasthan, historic interest places, like the Taj Mahal in Agra, receive millions of visitors every year, leading to the wear and tear of the monument and other forms of pollution (Das, 2017). Trekking and pilgrimage tourism takes place in sensitive environments that are also major spiritual retreats in the Himalayan region. The fragile environment of these areas is under threat from increased waste, deforestation, and shortage of water (Singh, 2018). The annual Amarnath Yatra in Jammu and Kashmir, attracting over 600,000 pilgrims, has raised concerns about the sustainability of the region's ecology (Jammu & Kashmir Tourism Department, 2019).

6. GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES AND SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

Acknowledging the negative impacts of overtourism, the Indian government and several state authorities have started taking initiatives for sustainable tourism. The Ministry of Tourism, Government of India's "Incredible India" campaign includes lesser-known destinations within its focus, distributing tourists more evenly throughout the country (Ministry of Tourism, 2020). Policies for eco-tourism are being framed in states like Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh, focusing on

habitat protection and including local communities in tourism plan formulations (Uttarakhand Tourism Development Board, 2019). One such means used is the imposition of a tourist cap on specific destinations. For example, a tourist cap has been set for the high altitude areas in the region of Sikkim to reduce the ecological pressure that may be applied through tourists (Sikkim Tourism, 2018). In the same manner, attempts are being made in developing strategies in the case of Goa to effectively manage coastal tourism that will enable protecting marine life and maintaining beach cleanliness (Goa Tourism Department, 2019)

Community involvement and understanding are essential for the fight against overtourism. Local populations who are assured or feel empowered from tourism have the ownership and, therefore, stewardship of their environment and cultural products. There have been the introduction of sensitization programs involving both tourists and locals in the inculcation of sustainable practices to enhance responsible tourism behavior (Chaudhary & Lama, 2018).

7. INSTANCES OF OVERTOURISM IN INDIA: FACTS AND FIGURES

S. No	State	Tourist Influx	Environmental Impact
1	GOA	In 2019, Goa attracted over 8 million tourists, including more than 900,000 international visitors (tourism.gov.in, 2019)	Waste Generation: Approximately 300 tonnes of solid waste are generated daily during peak tourist seasons (timesofindia.indiatimes.com, 2019)
		The state has a resident population of about 1.5 million, indicating a significant tourist-to-resident ratio (goatourism.gov.in, 2019)	Water Consumption: Tourist establishments account for nearly 16% of the state's total water usage (Goawater.org, 2019)
2	Kerala Backwaters (Alleppey)	Alleppey alone attracts around 1.5 million tourists annually (keralatourism.org, 2019)	Water Pollution: Studies have shown that houseboats contribute significantly to the pollution levels in the Vembanad Lake, with increased levels of coliform bacteria (keralapcb.org, 2019)
			Waste Management: Lack of adequate waste disposal systems has led to severe waste accumulation in water bodies (keralaenvironment.org, 2019)
3	Rajasthan (Jaipur, Udaipur, Jaisalmer)	Jaipur received over 4 million tourists in 2018, while Udaipur and Jaisalmer also saw significant numbers, with Udaipur attracting nearly 1.4 million tourists (rtdc.in, 2018)	Amber Fort in Jaipur experiences foot traffic of about 5,000 visitors per day during peak season (rtdc.in, 2018)
			Water Scarcity: Tourism activities contribute to the depletion of local water resources, which are already scarce in the arid region (rajasthanwater.org, 2018)
4	Himalayan Regions (Manali, Leh-Ladakh)	Leh-Ladakh saw over 327,000 tourists in 2018, a significant increase from previous years (leh-ladakhtourism.gov.in, 2018) Manali receives approximately 8 million tourists annually (himachaltourism.gov.in, 2018)	Waste Accumulation: In Leh, around 6,000 tonnes of waste are generated annually, much of which is from tourism activities (lehmunipality.org, 2018)
			Traffic Congestion: Increased vehicle traffic leads to air pollution and road degradation, especially in ecologically sensitive areas (himalayanenvironment.org, 2018)
5	Agra (Taj Mahal)	The Taj Mahal attracts about 8 million visitors annually (www.adaagra.org.in)	Wear and Tear: The high number of visitors has led to noticeable wear and tear on the marble structure (asi.nic.in, 2018)
			Air Pollution: Agra's air quality is severely impacted by industrial emissions and vehicle exhaust, leading to the discoloration of the monument (agrapollution.org, 2018)
6	J&K Amarnath Yatra	The annual Amarnath Yatra attracts between 300,000 and 600,000 pilgrims over a short period (amarnathjishrine.com, 2018)	Waste Generation: The pilgrimage generates significant amounts of waste, impacting the fragile Himalayan ecosystem (jkenvironment.org, 2018)
			Safety: The challenging terrain and large crowds often result in accidents and health emergencies

An example is Darjeeling, where this increased inflow has led to acute traffic congestion in the hilly town, especially during high tourist seasons, which has now virtually extended to seven months in a year. A town where almost 7,000 visitors add to its daily population on a regular basis, a reason why there are so many traffic congestion problems and reaching a short distance takes hours. The increase in tourists over the last few years also led to several other problems like scarcity of available water. The consumption of water in Darjeeling is almost double its supply, and, hence, the daily shortfall mounts to around 50 lakh litres of water. As such, the respective local authorities are therefore planning to come

up with alternative roads and increase the parking facilities to deal with such problems (Outlook Traveller, 2023). In addition, the effects of overtourism have also been witnessed in Ladakh. High tourist inflow has led to enormous pollution and environmental degradation. It has been a warming in the temperature with a rise in the number of vehicles, in turn increasing air pollution and temperature that rises the degree of glacial melt. Mass tourism has increased strain on the already fragile Ladakh ecosystem (Sojourn, 2023).

With an ever-iconic landmark being that of the Taj Mahal, Agra has established itself as a point of attraction for domestic and international tourists. This monument faces heavy crowding throughout the year and has led to different scams targeting these tourists; it thus motivates the challenge of overtourism being faced by this city. This becomes a stressful experience with the visitors, and throughout the year, it lessens the quality of the visitor experience (Sojourn, 2023). Some ways this overtourism is being managed are by promoting offbeat destinations, encouraging responsible tourism, and enhancing the infrastructure to better manage the flow of tourists. These are strategies that balance the economic benefits of tourism with that of preserving the environment and local quality of life.

8. CONCLUSION

Overtourism presents a complex and multifaceted challenge that threatens the sustainability of some of the world's most cherished tourist destinations. The rapid growth of global tourism, driven by affordability, digital influence, and increased mobility, has led to significant environmental, social, and economic impacts. These include environmental degradation, cultural erosion, and the displacement of local communities, highlighting the urgent need for strategic management. To mitigate these effects and ensure the long-term viability of tourism, a holistic approach is essential. This approach must integrate sustainable tourism practices, strategic planning, and active stakeholder collaboration. By balancing the economic benefits of tourism with the preservation of natural and cultural resources, destinations can maintain their unique identities while supporting local communities. The path forward requires innovative solutions that regulate visitor numbers, promote alternative destinations, and foster responsible tourism behaviour, ensuring that tourism remains a positive force for both hosts and visitors alike.

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